

An Algebraic Approach to General Divisibility Rules

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Abstract

An essential tool in number theory, divisibility rules have been documented for at least the first 1000 prime numbers. However, as the divisors increase in magnitude, these per-number rules decline, leading us to depend on more generalized rules to cover every number. Existing general algorithms for divisibility, such as osculation and those based on Pascal's test for divisibility, are of high computational complexity and, as such, quite difficult to scale. This paper introduces a generalized rule for all integers ending with a particular digit in base 10, as well as a universally generalized rule that is applicable to all integers in all bases. By deriving patterns based on a divisor's terminal digit and reversing what is typically used to prove such algorithms, I propose a singular, optimized divisibility rule of relatively simpler algebraic complexity and provide means to increasing these rules' efficiency.

1 Introduction

The study of divisibility is one of mathematics earliest pursuits [1], with documentation of divisibility algorithms dating as far back as 500 CE in the Babylonian Talmud. These heuristics became forerunners to methods such as "osculation", and despite the many centuries that have passed, these algorithms are still foundational in both elementary and algebraic number theory [1, 2], as well as finding modern applications in cryptography, data validation, and computational number manipulation.

Mathematicians such as Blaise Pascal and Joseph-Louis Lagrange successfully systematized these rules, moving them from simple heuristics to far more generalized methods. For instance, Pascal's work in the 17th century demonstrated that divisibility could be determined in any base B by evaluating a radix polynomial[3, 4]. Although this method works efficiently for smaller divisors or dividends of small magnitude, when it comes to much larger numbers, calculating a radix polynomial becomes much more computationally demanding [5, 6], or relies on prime factorization, which is itself a challenging problem for high-magnitude integers.

The main challenge here is the trade-off between an algorithm's generality and its scalability or efficiency [5]. Rules that adhere to a specific number or group of numbers remain efficient even at a high scale, while generalized rules become more and more computationally complex as one uses larger and larger integers. Although general criteria like Pascal's are exhaustive, setting them up requires one to calculate the modulus of each power of the base until a repetition occurs, which for some numbers, like 17, would often go through every number less than it.

While realistically speaking any method becomes nonviable if one scales the number high enough, the goal of this paper is to introduce general methods which are less computationally complex by relying on multiplication and subtraction for the algorithm rather than modulus, subsequently reducing the computational load and therefore increasing scalability. The paper first devises rules designed for numbers ending with a specific digit from base 10 and then introduces a Universal Divisibility Rule, which effectively works for every integer in any base, along with variations of this rule that become increasingly efficient for larger numbers. A section of this also addresses issues in algorithms based on addition by introducing a simple criterion to immediately verify divisibility when a fixed point is encountered.

2 The Digit-class Divisibility Rules

2.1 Introduction to Digit-class Divisibility Rules

The basis of these rules was the realization that for a class of numbers ending with a particular digit, a certain pattern can be observed for the divisibility rules specific to that class. Using these patterns, one can generalize these rules into one divisibility rule specific to that class[3, 7].

This section will describe and prove each of these patterns for digit classes 1 through 9. For each class, a closed-form expression for q is obtained, allowing each rule to be of the form $pt \pm qu$. Note that the following rules apply exclusively to base 10; for other bases, different digit-class rules are required[7].

2.2 Odd Digits and Formulating Divisibility Rules via Arithmetic Progressions

Note: The following proofs all rely on the fact that if the dividend $N = 10t + u$ is divisible by D , so that $N = Dk$ for some integer k , then any expression obtained by taking integer linear combinations of this defining equation remains a multiple of D [8, 9]. In particular, an expression of the form $D(at + bk)$, where $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}$, satisfies $D \mid D(at + bk)$. The display of these proofs also makes it easier to show how to prove the final divisibility rule for each digit class

2.2.1 Numbers ending with 1

To begin with, consider the divisibility rules for 11, 31, and 41, which is to subtract the last digit u 1, 3 and 4 times, respectively, from the rest of the number t .

Case $D = 11$:

1. $10t + u = 11k$
2. $-t + u = 11k - 11t$
3. $t - u = 11(t - k)$

Case $D = 31$:

1. $10t + u = 31k$
2. $30t + 3u = 93k$
3. $-t + 3u = 93k - 31t$
4. $t - 3u = 31(t - 3k)$

Case $D = 41$:

1. $10t + u = 41k$
2. $40t + 4u = 164k$
3. $-t + 4u = 164k - 41t$
4. $t - 4u = 41(t - 4k)$

Notice how to find that a number N is divisible by $10v + 1$ (D), one must multiply the last digit of that number u by v and subtract it from the remaining digits of the dividend t .

Case $D = 10v + 1$:

1. $10t + u = (10v + 1)k$
2. $10vt + vu = (10v + 1)kv$
3. $-t + vu = (10v + 1)kv - (10v + 1)t$
4. $t - vu = (10v + 1)(t - kv)$

Example:

For $D = 121$, $v = 12$ and $q = v = 12$.

$N = 1331$ (divisible): $133 - 1 \cdot 12 = 121$.

$N = 1442$ (not divisible): $144 - 2 \cdot 12 = 120$.

2.2.2 Numbers ending with 3

For $10v + 3$, 3 consecutive terms are prime: 3, 13, and 23. Their divisibility rules are to add the last digit u 1, 4, and 7 times, respectively, to the remaining number t .

Case $D = 3$:

1. $10t + u = 3k$
2. $t + u = 3k - 9t$
3. $t + u = 3(k - 3t)$

Case $D = 13$:

1. $10t + u = 13k$
2. $40t + 4u = 52k$
3. $t + 4u = 52k - 39t$
4. $t + 4u = 13(4k - 3t)$

Case $D = 23$:

1. $10t + u = 23k$
2. $70t + 7u = 161k$
3. $t + 7u = 161k - 69t$
4. $t + 7u = 23(7k - 3t)$

Notice how the coefficients of u appear to form a linear sequence. This sequence can then be made explicit by constructing a difference table (with $q = 1$ as the 0th term).

D	v	coefficient of u (q)	difference
3	0	1	
13	1	4	-3
23	2	7	-3

Table 1: Difference table for q when $D = 10v + 3$

Then, using arithmetic progression $q_v = q + (v - 1)d$, we find $q = 3v + 1$, so that if a number N is divisible by $10v + 3$ (D), adding its last digit u $3v + 1$ times to the rest of the number t will also return a multiple of $10v + 3$ (D).

Case $D = 10v + 3$:

1. $10t + u = (10v + 3)k$
2. $30vt + 10t + (3v + 1)u = (10v + 3)(3v + 1)k$
3. $t + (3v + 1)u = (10v + 3)(3v + 1)k - (30vt + 9t)$
4. $t + (3v + 1)u = (10v + 3)(3v + 1)k - 3(10v + 3)t$
5. $t + (3v + 1)u = (10v + 3)((3v + 1)k - 3t)$

Example:

For $D = 143$, $v = 14$ and $q = 3v + 1 = 43$.

$N = 2431$ (divisible): $243 + 1 \cdot 43 = 286 \rightarrow 28 + 6 \cdot 43 = 286$.

$N = 2192$ (not divisible): $219 + 2 \cdot 43 = 305$.

Note: Since this rule is addition based, some of the numbers will not be reduced further, acting as fixed points. For example, $28 + 6 \cdot 43 = 286$. In this case, it is a sign of divisibility. However, there are cases where the fixed point is not divisible. Later in this paper, methods for determining whether such a number is divisible will be explored.

2.2.3 Numbers ending with 7

Looking at the divisibility rules for 7, 17, and 27, the last digit u must be subtracted 2, 5, and 8 times, respectively, from the remaining number t .

Case $D = 7$:

1. $10t + u = 7k$
2. $20t + 2u = 14k$
3. $-t + 2u = 14k - 21t$
4. $t - 2u = 7(3t - 2k)$

Case $D = 17$:

1. $10t + u = 17k$
2. $50t + 5u = 85k$
3. $-t + 5u = 85k - 51t$
4. $t - 5u = 17(3t - 5k)$

Case $D = 27$:

1. $10t + u = 27k$
2. $80t + 8u = 216k$
3. $-t + 8u = 216k - 81t$
4. $t - 8u = 27(3t - 8k)$

D	v	coefficient of u (q)	difference
7	0	-2	
17	1	-5	3
27	2	-8	3

Table 2: Difference table for q when $D = 10v + 7$

Using an arithmetic progression, the coefficient of u is $-(3v + 2)$. That means if a number N is divisible by the number $10v + 7$ (D), truncating the unit digit u and then subtracting it $3v + 2$ times from the remaining number t will result in another multiple of $10v + 7$ (D).

Case $D = 10v + 7$:

1. $10t + u = (10v + 7)k$
2. $30vt + 20t + (3v + 2)u = (10v + 7)(3v + 2)k$
3. $-t + (3v + 2)u = (10v + 7)(3v + 2)k - (30vt + 21t)$
4. $-t + (3v + 2)u = (10v + 7)(3v + 2)k - 3(10v + 7)t$
5. $t - (3v + 2)u = (10v + 7)(3t - (3v + 2)k)$

Example:

For $D = 257$, $v = 25$ and $q = 3v + 2 = 77$.

$N = 10537$ (divisible): $1053 - 7 \cdot 77 = 514 \rightarrow 51 - 4 \cdot 77 = -257$.

$N = 10496$ (not divisible): $1049 - 6 \cdot 77 = 587 \rightarrow 58 - 7 \cdot 77 = -481$.

2.2.4 Numbers ending with 9

For $10v+9$, 9, 19, and 29 can be used to find the expression for q . Their divisibility rules are to take the unit digit u and add it 1, 2, and 3 times, respectively, to the remaining number t .

Case $D = 9$:	Case $D = 19$:	Case $D = 29$:
1. $10t + u = 9k$	1. $10t + u = 19k$	1. $10t + u = 29k$
2. $t + u = 9k - 9t$	2. $20t + 2u = 38k$	2. $30t + 3u = 87k$
3. $t + u = 9(k - t)$	3. $t + 2u = 38k - 19t$	3. $t + 3u = 87k - 29t$
	4. $t + 2u = 19(2k - t)$	4. $t + 3u = 29(3k - t)$

D	v	coefficient of u (q)	difference
9	0	-1	
19	1	-2	-1
29	2	-3	-1

Table 3: Difference table for q when $D = 10v + 9$

As observed, for a number N to be divisible by $10v + 9$ (D), removing the last digit u and adding it $v + 1$ times to the remaining number t will result in another multiple of $10v + 9$ (D).

Case $D = 10v + 9$:

1. $10t + u = (10v + 9)k$
2. $10vt + 10t + (v + 1)u = (10v + 9)(v + 1)k$
3. $t + (v + 1)u = (10v + 9)(v + 1)k - (10v + 9)t$
4. $t + (v + 1)u = (10v + 9)((v + 1)k - t)$

Example:

For $D = 369$, $v = 36$ and $q = v + 1 = 37$.

$N = 6642$ (divisible): $664 + 2 \cdot 37 = 738 \rightarrow 73 + 8 \cdot 37 = 369$.

$N = 6758$ (not divisible): $675 + 8 \cdot 37 = 971 \rightarrow 97 + 1 \cdot 37 = 134$.

2.3 Even Digits and Formulating Divisibility Rules Algebraically

Previously, the digit-class divisibility rules for odd numbers (excluding 5) were derived using preexisting divisibility algorithms. However, since all even numbers, with the exception of 2, are composite, there is consequently a lack of established divisibility rules for these numbers[7], rendering our previous method useless.

As such, a different approach is required. Rather than using arithmetic progression, the method developed in this section derives digit-class rules purely through algebra by examining the properties of both the dividend and the divisor. Additionally, this approach explains the variations in the coefficient of u and can be applied in other bases where few or no standard divisibility rules are available.

2.3.1 Formulating Divisibility Rules Algebraically

There are three steps to this method.

1. First, find the smallest multiple of $(10v + w)$ (where w represents any unit digit) that provides the most extreme unit digit possible and multiply it by t . This can be represented as $(10v + w)lt$, where l is an integer value by which $(10v + w)$ must be multiplied. (For even numbers, the most extreme unit digits possible are 8 and 2.)
2. Then, find the multiple of $10t$ (represented as $10qt$) such that subtracting $(10v + w)lt$ from it produces the smallest possible nonzero term involving t (for even digits, this, in absolute value, is $2t$). To determine the sign of this term, check whether $(10v + w)l$ has the highest or lowest possible unit digit. If the first is true, this term is positive. Otherwise, the term is negative. (Coincidentally, for all digit classes, the smallest possible nonzero coefficient of t matches $\gcd(10, w)$)[8]
3. Finally, dividing $10qt$ by $10t$ yields the coefficient of u (that is, q). (This is the amount by which both sides of $10t + u = (10v + w)k$ must be multiplied so that subtracting our multiple of $(10v + w)t$ from the right hand side gives our term for t .)
4. Essentially, we are reversing the method used to prove the digit-class divisibility rules.

For even divisors, the smallest (in absolute value) possible nonzero coefficient of t is 2, since all multiples end in an even digit and 2 is the lowest even digit. This term comes from subtracting a multiple ending with $2t$ or $8t$ with the nearest multiple of $10t$: multiples ending with $2t$ will be greater than the nearest multiple of $10t$ and, as a result, produce a coefficient of $-2t$, while those ending with $8t$ will be less than the nearest multiple of $10t$, producing a coefficient of $+2t$. In practice, the coefficient corresponding to the smallest such multiple is used.

Note: The coefficient of t in the final algorithm will always be positive and the sign for the u -term will be flipped correspondingly.

2.3.2 Numbers ending with 2

For this class, the smallest multiple with the most extreme unit digit possible is the number itself, $10v + 2$. As such, the amount subtracted from both sides of the equation is $(10v + 2)t \rightarrow 10vt + 2t$. We choose an expression such that subtracting $10vt + 2t$ yields the term $-2t$, since the unit digit of $10v + 2$ is the lowest possible unit digit. Let X denote this expression.

$$X - (10vt + 2t) = -2t$$

$$X = 10vt$$

Finally, according to the method, dividing by $10t$ yields the coefficient of u .

$$\frac{10vt}{10t} = v$$

Case $D = 10v + 2$:

1. $10t + u = (10v + 2)k$
2. $10vt + vu = (10v + 2)kv$
3. $-2t + vu = (10v + 2)kv - (10v + 2)t$
4. $2t - vu = (10v + 2)(t - kv)$

Example:

For $D = 342$, $v = 34$ and $q = v = 34$.

$N = 8208$ (divisible): $820 \cdot 2 - 8 \cdot 34 = 1368 \rightarrow 136 \cdot 2 - 8 \cdot 34 = 0$

$N = 8004$ (not divisible): $800 \cdot 2 - 4 \cdot 34 = 1464 \rightarrow 146 \cdot 2 - 4 \cdot 34 = 156$.

2.3.3 Numbers ending with 4

For numbers ending with 4, their second multiple is the lowest multiple that ends with 8, so we subtract $20vt + 8t$ from both sides. Since the unit digit is now the highest possible, the difference must be $+2t$. Using this, we determine X .

$$X - (20vt + 8t) = 2t$$

$$X = 20vt + 10t$$

Dividing $20vt + 10t$ by $10t$ provides the coefficient of u .

$$\frac{20vt + 10t}{10t} = 2v + 1$$

Case $D = 10v + 4$:

1. $10t + u = (10v + 4)k$
2. $20vt + 10t + (2v + 1)u = (10v + 4)(2v + 1)k$
3. $2t + (2v + 1)u = (10v + 4)(2v + 1)k - (20vt + 8t)$
4. $2t + (2v + 1)u = (10v + 4)(2v + 1)k - 2(10v + 4)t$
5. $2t + (2v + 1)u = (10v + 4)((2v + 1)k - 2t)$

Example:

For $D = 544$, $v = 54$ and $q = 2v + 1 = 109$.

$N = 25024$ (divisible): $2502 \cdot 2 + 4 \cdot 109 = 5440 \rightarrow 544 \cdot 2 + 0 \cdot 109 = 1088 \rightarrow 108 \cdot 2 + 8 \cdot 109 = 1088$.

$N = 24274$ (not divisible): $2427 \cdot 2 + 4 \cdot 109 = 5290 \rightarrow 529 \cdot 2 + 0 \cdot 109 = 1058 \rightarrow 105 \cdot 2 + 8 \cdot 109 = 1082$.

2.3.4 Numbers ending with 6

As in digit-class 4, multiplying $2t$ by $10v + 6$ yields the multiple $20vt + 12t$, which provides the most extreme nonzero unit digit possible (in this case, the lowest even digit). This can then be subtracted from a multiple of $10t$ and results in the term $-2t$. With that in mind, let us determine X .

$$X - (20vt + 12t) = -2t$$

$$X = 20vt + 10t$$

Divide this expression by $10t$ to obtain the coefficient of u .

$$\frac{20vt + 10t}{10t} = 2v + 1$$

Case $D = 10v + 6$:

1. $10t + u = (10v + 6)k$
2. $20vt + 10t + (2v + 1)u = (10v + 6)(2v + 1)k$
3. $-2t + (2v + 1)u = (10v + 6)(2v + 1)k - (20vt + 12t)$
4. $-2t + (2v + 1)u = (10v + 6)(2v + 1)k - 2(10v + 6)t$
5. $2t - (2v + 1)u = (10v + 6)(2t - (2v + 1)k)$

Example:

For $D = 776$, $v = 77$ and $q = 2v + 1 = 155$.

$N = 9312$ (divisible): $931 \cdot 2 - 2 \cdot 155 = 1552 \rightarrow 155 \cdot 2 - 2 \cdot 155 = 0$.

$N = 9788$ (not divisible): $978 \cdot 2 - 8 \cdot 155 = 716$.

2.3.5 Numbers ending with 8

For $10v+8$, deriving its rule is similar to $10v+2$, since 8 can be directly subtracted from 10 to obtain 2. However, since this time it provides the highest possible even digit 8, subtracting $10vt + 8t$ from the expression X provides the term $+2t$.

$$X - (10vt + 8t) = 2t$$

$$X = 10vt + 10t$$

Dividing this by $10t$ yields the coefficient of u .

$$\frac{10vt + 10t}{10t} = v + 1$$

Case $10v + 8$:

1. $10t + u = (10v + 8)k$
2. $10vt + 10t + (v + 1)u = (10v + 8)(v + 1)k$
3. $2t + (v + 1)u = (10v + 8)(v + 1)k - (10v + 8)t$
4. $2t + (v + 1)u = (10v + 8)((v + 1)k - t)$

Example:

For $D = 688$, $v = 68$ and $q = v + 1 = 69$.

$N = 32336$ (divisible): $3233 \cdot 2 + 6 \cdot 69 = 6880 \rightarrow 688 \cdot 2 + 0 \cdot 69 = 1376 \rightarrow 137 \cdot 2 + 6 \cdot 69 = 688$.

$N = 32066$ (not divisible): $3206 \cdot 2 + 6 \cdot 69 = 6826 \rightarrow 682 \cdot 2 + 6 \cdot 69 = 1778 \rightarrow 177 \cdot 2 + 8 \cdot 69 = 906$.

2.3.6 Numbers ending with 5

Digit 5 was kept last as the coefficient of t will be even larger, due to multiples of five all ending with 5 and 0. So, our most extreme nonzero coefficient of t is always 5. Although this may be tricky for an efficient divisibility rule, for a general rule, it is the best one can do.

For $10v + 5$, the lowest multiple of $10v + 5$ that ends with 5 is itself. Although taking $5t$ also provides a divisibility algorithm, selecting $-5t$ provides a simpler and more efficient rule. So, subtracting $10vt + 5t$ from X gives us $-5t$.

$$X - (10vt + 5t) = -5t$$

$$X = 10vt$$

Dividing this by $10t$, we can find the coefficient of u .

$$\frac{10vt}{10t} = v$$

Case $10v + 5$:

1. $10t + u = (10v + 5)k$
2. $10vt + vu = (10v + 5)kv$
3. $-5t + vu = (10v + 5)kv - (10v + 5)t$
4. $5t - vu = (10v + 5)(t - kv)$

Example:

For $D = 235$, $v = 23$ and $q = v = 23$.

$N = 7285$ (divisible): $728 \cdot 5 - 23 \cdot 5 = 3525 \rightarrow 352 \cdot 5 - 23 \cdot 5 = 1645 \rightarrow 164 \cdot 5 - 23 \cdot 5 = 705 \rightarrow 70 \cdot 5 - 23 \cdot 5 = 235$.

$N = 7505$ (not divisible): $750 \cdot 5 - 23 \cdot 5 = 3635 \rightarrow 363 \cdot 5 - 23 \cdot 5 = 1700 \rightarrow 170 \cdot 5 - 23 \cdot 0 = 850 \rightarrow 85 \cdot 5 - 23 \cdot 0 = 425 \rightarrow 42 \cdot 5 - 23 \cdot 5 = 95$.

3 The Universal Divisibility Rule and Fixed Points

3.1 The Universal Divisibility Rule

Previously, we have focused on general divisibility rules for a group of specific numbers. Now, using the same logic, we can create a rule for every number, regardless of the base.

3.1.1 The Raw Universal Divisibility Rule

Take $Bv + w$, where B is the base of the number system, w is the unit digit of the divisor, and v is what remains after truncation. Since both B and w are arbitrary, there is no way to determine what the *lowest* unit digit produced from a multiple of $Bv + w$ is. Thus, we will have to take $-wt$ as our term for t and $Bvt + wt$ as the multiple subtracted from the nearest multiple of B .

$$X - (Bv + w)t = -wt$$

$$X = Bvt$$

Now, all that is left to do is find out by what Bt needs to be multiplied to obtain Bvt , and then use it in our proof.

$$\frac{Bvt}{Bt} = v$$

Case $D = Bv + w$:

1. $Bt + u = (Bv + w)k$
2. $Bvt + vu = (Bv + w)kv$
3. $-wt + vu = (Bv + w)kv - (Bv + w)t$
4. $wt - vu = (Bv + w)(t - kv)$

It is likely that since 1, 2, and 5 are all factors of 10, the base of the number system, the simplest way to frame their digit-class rules is the same as derived from the universal rule. Similar behavior should be expected for other values of B

Note that this rule does not work for numbers less than B , as their v would be 0 and subsequently all inputs will output a multiple of w even when the number is not divisible.

3.1.2 The Optimized Universal Divisibility Rule

Although the Universal Divisibility Rule is efficient for numbers of the same order of magnitude (40 and 140), it is quite inefficient when the dividend and divisor have a huge difference in magnitude (181232 and 21). Similar inefficiencies can be observed for numbers where w is significantly higher than v , for example 19.

Testing 435093 for 23:

$$\begin{aligned}3 \cdot 43509 - 2 \cdot 3 &= 130521 \\3 \cdot 13052 - 2 \cdot 1 &= 39154 \\3 \cdot 3915 - 2 \cdot 4 &= 11737 \\3 \cdot 1173 - 2 \cdot 7 &= 3505 \\3 \cdot 350 - 2 \cdot 5 &= 1040 \\3 \cdot 104 - 2 \cdot 0 &= 312 \\3 \cdot 31 - 2 \cdot 2 &= 89 \\3 \cdot 8 - 2 \cdot 9 &= 6\end{aligned}$$

435093 is not divisible by 23.

Testing 435091 for 23:

$$\begin{aligned}3 \cdot 43509 - 2 \cdot 1 &= 130525 \\3 \cdot 13052 - 2 \cdot 5 &= 39146 \\3 \cdot 3914 - 2 \cdot 6 &= 11730 \\3 \cdot 1173 - 2 \cdot 0 &= 3519 \\3 \cdot 351 - 2 \cdot 9 &= 1035 \\3 \cdot 103 - 2 \cdot 5 &= 299 \\3 \cdot 29 - 2 \cdot 9 &= 69 \\3 \cdot 6 - 2 \cdot 9 &= 0\end{aligned}$$

435091 is divisible by 23.

As seen in the example, it took 8 steps before it was clear if D divides N or not, since the amount subtracted each step is relatively negligible. Ideally, for maximum reduction, we need both terms to be of a similar order of magnitude, which we can achieve by substituting our values differently. Although we typically truncate N and take values of u as all nonnegative values less than B , any value can be taken as u and t as long as $Bt + u$ still adds up correctly and both variables are integers. Since 23 gives values of v and w as 2 and 3, respectively, partitioning 435091 by taking u and t as 35093 (or 35091) and 40000 will produce terms of similar magnitude, which, in theory, maximizes the reduction. Let us see if this holds true in practice.

Testing 435093 for 23:

$$\begin{aligned}3 \cdot 40000 - 2 \cdot 35093 &= 49814 \\3 \cdot 4000 - 2 \cdot 9814 &= -7628 \\3 \cdot -700 - 2 \cdot -628 &= -844 \\3 \cdot -80 - 2 \cdot -44 &= -152 \\3 \cdot -10 - 2 \cdot -52 &= 74 \\3 \cdot 7 - 2 \cdot 4 &= 13\end{aligned}$$

so 435093 is not divisible.

Testing 435091 for 23:

$$\begin{aligned}3 \cdot 40000 - 2 \cdot 35091 &= 49818 \\3 \cdot 4000 - 2 \cdot 9818 &= -7636 \\3 \cdot -700 - 2 \cdot -636 &= -828 \\3 \cdot -80 - 2 \cdot -28 &= -184 \\3 \cdot -10 - 2 \cdot -84 &= 138 \\3 \cdot 10 - 2 \cdot 38 &= -46 \\3 \cdot -4 - 2 \cdot -6 &= 0\end{aligned}$$

so 435091 is divisible.

so 435093 is not divisible. Also note that technically speaking, this can be applied to subtraction-based digit-class divisibility rules

This method works well for its simplicity; as you can see, the values initially decrease drastically without too much calculation. It also becomes clearer earlier on whether the number is divisible or not without finishing the entire process. This is by no means the most efficient variation of this rule. For example, we can also partition $10v + w$ more efficiently, or we could change how the numbers themselves are truncated by taking B as 100 or 1000. However, this method is the simplest to understand with quite efficient results and thus is called the "optimized" universal rule.

3.1.3 The Terminal Universal Divisibility Rule

This rule relies on the principle that for every integer N , where $N = Dk$ and $D = Bv + w$, there exists a way to partition $N = Bt + u$ such that $wt - vu = 0$, terminating the sequence in a single step. We can prove this by understanding that since $N = k(Bv + w) = B(kv) + kw$, one can take the values for t and u as kv and kw , respectively. By substituting these values into the universal rule, we find $wt - vu = kv \cdot w - kw \cdot v = 0$.

However, practically identifying these partitions is challenging, where brute force is seemingly the only possible method. However, there are 3 properties to consider that will narrow down the search:

1. t is added B times to u to obtain N , so each digit of N must be congruent to the sum of the digit of u in the same place value and the digit of t in the previous place value (mod B).
2. Each digit of u times v must be congruent with each digit of t times w (mod B).
3. Since t is an integer and cannot have decimals, the last digit of N is equivalent to the last digit of u and will serve as a fixed starting point for the method.

Using these properties, the following method can be used to obtain the partition.

1. Truncate the last digit of N to obtain the last digit of u . This is the starting current digit of u .
2. Multiply the current digit of u by v to obtain the current place value of kwv ($u = kw$).
3. Set $wx - y_o = By + kwv$ and solve for integers x and y , where x is the current digit of t , y ensures that x is a single digit number, and y_o is the value of y obtained previously (in the first iteration, it has a value of 0).

4. Subtract x from the next digit of N to get the next digit of u . If x is greater than the next digit of N , the typical borrowing rules apply. Ensure that the changes made to the following digits of N are maintained.
5. Repeat this process for the next digit of u .

Example: $N = 4453905$, $D = 789$

Reminder: Each digit of t is equal to the value of x at the corresponding step.
 Note: If a digit of t is greater than a digit of N , use the borrowing method

Iterations: **6** **5** **4** **3** **2** **1** **0**
 N : 4 4 5 3 9 0 5
 t : - 4 4 0 3 1 0
 u : 0 0 5 0 8 0 5 \longrightarrow $440310 \times 9 - 50805 \times 78 = 0$

<p>1. $5 \times 78 = 390$ $9x = 10y + 390$ $x = 0, y = -39$</p>	<p>3. $8 \times 78 = 624$ $9x - 3 = 10y + 624$ $9x = 10y + 627$ $x = 3, y = -60$</p>	<p>5. $5 \times 78 = 390$ $9x - 6 = 10y + 390$ $9x = 10y + 396$ $x = 4, y = -36$</p>
<p>2. $0 \times 78 = 0$ $9x - 39 = 10y + 0$ $9x = 10y + 39$ $x = 1, y = -3$</p>	<p>4. $0 \times 78 = 0$ $9x - 60 = 10y + 0$ $9x = 10y + 60$ $x = 0, y = -6$</p>	<p>6. $0 \times 78 = 0$ $9x - 36 = 10y + 0$ $9x = 10y + 36$ $x = 4, y = 0$</p>

Figure 1: An example of the Terminal Divisibility Rule for reference. Each iteration and calculation step share a colored number

This method is very powerful and computationally less burdensome, as it only relies on simple multiplication and algebra and needs to be repeated for each digit of N minus the last. Additionally, k is preserved, unlike in other divisibility rules. Unfortunately, this method is only feasible for numbers that satisfy $\gcd(w, B) = 1$. This is because if we look at the unit digits of multiples of w from 0 to $(B - 1)w$, the same sequence repeats itself $\gcd(w, B)$ times[10], so there are $\gcd(w, B)$ values of x that satisfy the equation $wx - y_o = By + kwv$. As a result, we have $\gcd(w, B)$ possible values for x each step, so the total number of possible partitions is $\gcd(w, B)^{n-1}$, where n is the total number of digits of N . Finding the right one is simply not feasible for high order numbers.

3.2 Investigating the Divisibility of Fixed Points

Earlier in this paper, we encountered digit-class rules in which fixed points can appear. This section will explain and show how to tell if a fixed point is divisible or not using only their values of w and u . A fixed point here refers to a number N that is mapped onto itself by the associated digit-class divisibility algorithm.

3.2.1 Creating the relationships

The divisibility rules in which fixed points can occur are, as listed below, for 3, 4, 8 and 9:

$$t + (3v + 1)u = (10v + 3)((3v + 1)k - 3t)$$

$$2t + (2v + 1)u = (10v + 4)((2v + 1)k - 2t)$$

$$2t + (v + 1)u = (10v + 8)((v + 1)k - t)$$

$$t + (v + 1)u = (10v + 9)((v + 1)k - t)$$

We now need to equate LHS with $10t + u$ to create an equation that predicts fixed points.

$$t + (3v + 1)u = 10t + u$$

$$2t + (2v + 1)u = 10t + u$$

$$2t + (v + 1)u = 10t + u$$

$$t + (v + 1)u = 10t + u$$

Finally, we rearrange these equations to get t in terms of u .

$$t = \frac{vu}{3} \quad t = \frac{vu}{4} \quad t = \frac{vu}{8} \quad t = \frac{vu}{9}$$

Surprisingly, the denominator of the equation is exactly equal to w

If we plot these equations with u on the x -axis and t on the y -axis, we find that for most values of v , when the graph goes through a point with an integer value of x and y , these numbers form a multiple of $10v + w$, because the gradient is fractional. However, when $v \equiv 0 \pmod{w}$, the gradient becomes an integer, causing numbers that are not multiples of $10v + w$ to also be represented by integer values of x and y . This means that we need a way to tell whether or not a fixed point is divisible.

3.2.2 Fixed Point Divisibility Rule

Although the graph has a range of $f(x) \in \mathbb{R}$, we can restrict the domain in a way that still meets the rule's requirements: Since u represents the unit digit, the only values of u that we will use are between 1 and 9. So, we can restrict the domain to $0 \leq x \leq 9$.

When we look at these new graphs, we observe that since x is restricted to only single digit numbers, the last digit of divisible numbers in this range must be divisible by w . So, if a fixed point is encountered, check that u is divisible by w . If it is, the number is divisible!

4 Applications

Both the Universal and the Digit-Class Divisibility Rules provide the framework needed to determine a divisibility rule for any arbitrary integer. This framework explains the behavior of the coefficients of t and u , and, with B , v , and w , predicts terminating behavior, fixed points, and efficiency or feasibility (although this in particular also depends on how N and D are split).

Additionally, the rules are formulated independently of the base, meaning that we can apply the same frameworks without conversion to other number systems, which is ideal for understanding divisibility behavior in unexplored bases. Because the rules are structured algebraically, divisibility algorithms can be derived and generated symbolically and can be supported by automated reasoning on the rule's accuracy. While the Universal Divisibility

Rule is by no means the most efficient method for large-scale computation, it provides a great starting point for an arbitrary integer in an arbitrary base, and since many familiar divisibility rules are actually predicted by either the DCDRs or UDR, they all can fit well in an educational setting.

5 Conclusion and Future Direction

This paper introduced a framework for constructing divisibility rules, beginning with rules specific to the digits of base 10 and then going further to make a Universal Divisibility Rule applicable to any integer of any base. By reversing the method used to structure proofs of divisibility rules, this paper provides a simple method for generating rules instead of relying on remembering prior rules. Additionally, it explains the behavior of coefficients, identifies ways to improve efficiency, and shows how to deal with phenomena such as fixed points.

While the Universal Divisibility Rule is not optimized for large-scale computing[5, 6], it offers an algebraically simple and consistent starting point for analyzing divisibility. Furthermore, its incredible flexibility in how the numerator and denominator can be partitioned allows one to easily improve its efficiency, as seen with the Optimized and Terminal variants.

Future work may focus on refining optimization strategies, particularly by developing a faster and more efficient method for selecting optimal partitions for the numerator and denominator. Extending this to explicitly specify efficiency bounds or to compare the performance across different bases would help determine how computationally viable this particular method is.

More broadly, this method offers both an educational bridge between basic divisibility rules and higher number theory and a foundation for further exploration into general digit-class algorithms.

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